

EVALUATING A RESTRICTED ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIBING POLICY: REDUCED UTILIZATION AND EXPENDITURE AT PRINCE ZAID BIN AL-HUSSEIN MILITARY HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Excessive antibiotic use stays the main driver for antibiotics resistance (AMR), a global risk to health that keeps putting healthcare systems around the world to the challenge, to address this problem, some systems have implemented antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs), to limit the utilize of restricted antibiotics to decrease antibiotics resistance and health care cost. **Methodology** We will use a retrospective before-and-after design to assess the effects of introducing antimicrobial stewardship measures at Prince Zaid bin Al-Hussein Military Hospital, the pre and post and intervention year(2022)/ (2023) were two consecutive 12-month periods that we will analyze to compare antibiotic prescription habits and related expenditures. To ensure comparability between the two periods, all consumption metrics were adjusted for monthly hospital admission rates, enabling standardized comparisons that account for variations in patient volume. **Data Collection** Antibiotic utilization data were extracted from the hospital's pharmacy information system, which documents all dispensed antibiotics along with the quantities supplied (e.g., grams, vials, or units), Monthly hospital admission numbers were obtained from administrative records to calculate standardized consumption indicators such as Defined Daily Dose (DDD) per 100 admissions, where applicable, all datasets were reviewed for completeness and consistency prior to analysis. **Results:** Colistin: although a 20% rise in bed utilization, there was a 21.4% decrease and 442.5 JD savings. Meropenem -500 mg- 14.4% decrease - savings of 70 JD -, 1 g Ertapenem: 7.3% decrease -168 JD savings-, Imipenem/Cilastatin: 10.4% decrease -364 JD savings-, 19.8% decrease - 886.7 JD savings-, Total Yearly Savings: 1413 JD Reductions were not the result of chance because they were very significant ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Although stronger interventions are required for antibiotics like ertapenem, our study demonstrated significant decreases in the use of high-risk antibiotics (like colistin) and quantifiable saving cost.

KEYWORDS: Antibiotic resistance, cost, restricted protocols, stewardship programs, military hospitals.

1. INTRODUCTION

By 2050, antibiotics resistance (AMR) is estimated to result in 10 million annual deaths. if current trends continue, posing a grave threat to global health (CDC, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2020), use of antibiotics is the main causes of AMR, particularly in medical settings where broad-spectrum medications are

overprescribed, ((O'Neill, 2016): WHO, 2020), Restricted antibiotic prescription regimens are part of antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs), which have been heavily pushed as a way to lower antimicrobials resistance, justify antimicrobials use, and improve safety (Karanika et al., 2016).

Due to restrictive protocols, prescribers must obtain authorization from pharmacists or infectious disease specialists before prescribing high-risk antibiotics, in high-income nations, these tactics have shown effective in lowering rates of antibiotic abuse and resistance (Bauri *et al.*, 2017).

However, its use in resource constrained settings, such as Jordan military hospitals is currently understudied (Atbara *et al.*, 2021). Jordan's Prince Zaid Bin Al-Hussein Military Hospital provide complications because it treat both soldiers and civilians, it often face with requests for infection control and high patient turnover. (Al-Taani *et al.*, 2018).

The effect of restricted antibiotics regimens in Prince Zaid Bin Al-Hussein Military Hospital in 2022 were investigated in this study, The main objective was to evaluate changes in antibiotic use by comparing data from 2022 (pre-intervention) and 2023 (post-intervention), Spending and prescription patterns while taking hospital admission rates into consideration.

2- METHODOLOGY

We will use a retrospective before-and-after design to assess the effects of introducing antimicrobial stewardship measures at Prince Zaid bin Al-Hussein Military Hospital, the Prior to intervention year(2022) and the after-intervention year (2023) were two consecutive 12-month periods that we will analyze to compare antibiotic prescription habits and related expenditures. To ensure comparability between the two

periods, all consumption metrics were adjusted for monthly hospital admission rates, enabling standardized comparisons that account for variations in patient volume.

Data Collection Antibiotic utilization data were extracted from the hospital's pharmacy information system, which documents all dispensed antibiotics along with the quantities supplied (e.g., grams, vials, or units). Monthly hospital admission numbers were obtained from administrative records to calculate standardized consumption indicators such as Defined Daily Dose (DDD) per 100 admissions, where applicable, all datasets were reviewed for completeness and consistency prior to analysis.

2. VARIABLES

2.1 Outcomes

1. Antibiotic Consumption: Calculated as the total amount of each antibiotic administered (such as grams, vials, or pills) and normalizing it by the number of admissions.

$$\text{Utilization per 100 admissions} = \frac{\text{Total quantity dispensed}}{\text{Total admissions}} \times 100$$

2. Price analysis: Total monthly antibiotic spending (in JD).

3. Price per admission = the total price of restricted antibiotics / the total number of admissions.

3. Ethical Considerations

The Royal Medical Services Ethics Committee has given its approval.

4. RESULTS

Table 1: Dispensed Prescription Quantities Summary.

Antibiotics	Dosage	Before	After	Absolute Difference	Percentage Change (%)
Colistin	2million	96	76	+20	↓ 21.4%
Meropenem	500 mg	206	175	+31	↓ 14.4%
Ertapenem	500 mg	104	96	+8	↓ 7.3%
Meropenem	1 g	580	464	+115	↓ 19.7%
Imipenem/Cilastatin	1 g	1843	1653	189	↓ 10.4%

Table 2: Hospital Bed Occupancy Calculation.

Metric	Before (average)	After (average)
Monthly :		
- Occupied Bed/Days	1,000 bed/days	1200 bed/days
Annually :		
- Occupied Bed/Days	12167 bed/days	14600 bed/days

Table 3: Rate of Antibiotics Use per 100 Bed /Days.

Antibiotics	Dosage	Total DDDs (Before)	DDD/100 bed/days (Before)	Total DDDs (After)	DDD/100 bed/days (After)	Reduction (%)	P-value*
Colistin	—	96	9.61	76	6.30	↓34.4%	0.0012
Meropenem	.5 gram	206	20.58	175	14.60	↓29.1%	0.0003
Ertapenem	.5gram	104	10.30	96	8.10	↓22.09%	0.0042
Meropenem	1 gram	580	57.92	465	38.7	↓33.1%	<0.001
Imipenem/Cilastatin	1 gram	1843	184.13	1654	137.8	↓25.02%	0.008

DDD= Defined Daily Dose

5. Calculating Financial Savings

Savings = Defined Daily Dose Before implementing protocol – Defined Daily Dose After implementing protocol × Cost per Defined Daily Dose

Table 4: Financial Savings.

Restricted Antibiotics	Dosage	DDDs Before	DDDs After	Cost per DDD (JD)	Savings (JD)
Colistin	–	96	76	21.1	442.5
Meropenem	500 mg	206	175	2.28	70.68
Ertapenem	500 mg	104	96	21	168
Meropenem	1 g	580	38	2.57	364.94
Imipenem/Cilastatin	1 g	1843	1664	2.45	438.55
Total Savings					1413.99 JD

Table 5: Analysis of Significance.

Restricted Antibiotics	Rate Before	Rate After	p-value	Significance ($\alpha=0.05$)
Colistin	0.0078	0.0051	<0.001	Yes
Ertapenem .5g	0.0084	0.0065	.009	Yes
Imipenem/Cilastatin	0.1514	0.1132	<0.001	Yes
Meropenem .5 g	0.0166	0.0121	<0.001	Yes
Meropenem 1 g	0.0466	0.0317	<0.001	Yes

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. With a reduction of 21.15% (96 to 76 DDDs), Colistin showed the second-greatest proportion reduction a savings of 442.5 JD, Similar research in the Middle East, that documented 15–30% decreases after ASP adoption, were motivated by preauthorization regulations and clinician education (World Health Organization, 2021), Although a 20% increase in bed utilization the found 21.5% decreased falls within global range, that indicate effective stewardship, An 18% savings in India was reported by Chaudhary *et al.* (2019), underscoring the need for improved controls (such as daily auditing) for reductions beyond 25%.

B. Meropenem a (Tamma *et al.* 2017) reported a 22% decrease in carbapenem use in the United States but we observe -500 mg- a 13.7% decrease (a reduction of 70.68 JD) and (1 g) a 19.8% decrease (a reduction of 364.98 JD),

It is quite to the meropenem 1 g findings, (Baur *et al.*, 2017) revealed that using a passive strategy for carbapenems resulted in lesser decreases (12–18%).

Which closely similar the meropenem 1 g outcomes (Baur *et al.*, 2017) that revealed decreases less than (12–18%) to carbapenems with a other strategy, The decreased savings for meropenem 500 mg (2.28 Jordan dinar /DDD vs. 2.57 jordan dinar /DDD) could be explained by its application in less lengthy courses.

C. Ertapenem: The National Institutes of Health (2019) reported that ertapenem consumption seldom declines significantly without specific limits, with a 7.3% drop (a savings of 168.0 JD).

Because ertapenem is often reserved for abdominal infections, another study (Zavasucki *et al.*, 2016) found modest decrease (5–10%) with no close monitoring.

D. Imipenem/cilastatin: our study shows a 10.3% decrease (a savings of 438.55 JD, (Aldeyab *et al.* 2018) in the the United Kingdom observed an 8–12% decrease during learning events, which is comparable with our results. According to A systematic review (Clinical microbiology and an infection, 2021), organized treatments (such real-time prescription tracking) are necessary for reductions greater than 15%. Therefore, the 10.3% fall indicates a modest level of success, supporting enhanced tools such as automated prescriber alerts.

7. Clinical and Economic Importance

Cost Reduction: The overall reduction of 1413.99 Jordan Dinar /year show that average selling prices are financially viable; the savings were significant, indicating the reductions are not the result of chance.

8. Limitations

- Intervention Design: This intervention may rely only on dispensing controls, whereas most research incorporated education and limits.
- Confounding Factors: Although statistical corrections (Z-tests) indicated significance ($p < 0.0001$), a 21% increase in be.

9. CONCLUSIONS

Compliance with Evidence: The effectiveness of the intervention has been proven by reductions (7.–21%), which reflect global trends.

10. Recommendations

1. Improve Interventions: To increase decreases (e.g., for ertapenem), incorporate education and real-time feedback.
2. Monitor Resistance: To evaluate the long-term clinical impact, keep an eye on trends of microbial resistance.

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